

Voice-Driven Bakery Assistant: Handsfree Bakery Operations Management with Enhanced Security

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Abstract - Hassle-free technologies are inevitable in the modern world for ensuring user convenience. Users are attracted by technologies that are more innovative and time-saving. In this context the implementation of a voice driven bakery assistant with face recognition and OTP mechanism plays an important role in food-based businesses, such as a bakery web application, where the users depend on the application to order products quickly and conveniently. Many times, these applications fail to implement a voice-based system that can provide a fast and hands-free operation to the user. The said voice driven system has a face recognition system that will help the user to register their face by linking their account with their face and can gain access to their account then onwards. For an additional piece of security, the user will be provided with an OTP instantly on their screen where the user must enter it on the screen for a second level of security. Such a system is vital, as the voice-driven system has equal potential as a web application feature and as a robot in a POS terminal. Even though speech recognition technologies have existed in the industry for a long time, e-commerce applications rarely use this technology, which can have significant advantages in enhancing the UI/UX experience. The system follows a three-tier architecture, which includes the presentation, application, and data tiers.

Keywords-OTP, POS, UI/UX, AI, RTC, VGG

I. INTRODUCTION

The research paper aims to implement a Voice-driven bakery assistant system that can provide a hands-free operation for an e-commerce platform such as a bakery web application. Unlike traditional voice recognition systems, the voice-driven assistant has a face recognition system that

can register the user's face with their account and authenticate them from then onwards. It also features an OTP system that acts as a second level of security. These two levels of security make this system ideal for implementation in both applications and as a robotic assistant in a POS terminal. The voice-driven assistant follows a three-tier architecture, which includes the presentation, application, and data layers. The presentation layer consists of a voice interface, a visual feedback system, Real-time cart updates, and a face registration/verification UI. The application layer deals with command processing, Natural language understanding, face recognition processing, cart management, and order processing. The data tier consists of Firebase Real-time Database, file system storage for face images, session storage, and product inventory management. With such a system, users can securely gain access, order products from the database, and manage their carts. Admins can view sales statistics, generate transaction reports and charts, and access other sales features This system can effectively minimize browsing time and provide users with reliable content.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

E-commerce platforms are integrating a variety of technologies and tools to direct customers to their platforms. They regularly update their systems and platforms to remain competitive in the industry. Voice recognition and Its applications are often used as standalone platforms. If integrated with e-commerce and business platforms, they could introduce significant changes and automation capabilities.

A study conducted by [1] in 2018 suggests that, in most scenarios, voice assistant platforms are used for tasks such as answering questions, controlling home automation

devices, managing media playback, and handling basic email functions. Some examples of such systems include Amazon Alexa, Apple Siri, and Google Assistant.

A study conducted by [2] in 2023 states that the advent of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies like ChatGPT has advanced and enhanced virtual assistant products and services.

[3] The first digital virtual assistant installed on a smartphone was Apple's Siri, introduced with the iPhone 4S. [4] In 2001, Colloquis launched Smarter Child on platforms like MSN Messenger and AIM. Smarter Child was entirely text-based and could play games, check the weather, look up facts, etc.

Research by [5][6][7] discusses Cortana, a voice-only assistant with single-factor authentication. This voice-driven system processes user commands to perform common tasks such as checking the weather and making calls. Cortana has privacy concerns due to its lack of multi-factor authentication. The proposed voice assistant addresses security concerns by implementing multi-level authentication and customization for the bakery platform.

III.METHODOLOGY

The voice-driven system follows a three-tier architecture, as discussed earlier. Since the system follows a tiered architecture, it is more reliable. The tiers include the presentation tier, application tier, and data tier. The presentation tier performs the responsibilities of voice interface, visual feedback system, Real-time cart updates, and face registration and verification UI. The second tier is the application tier, which performs command processing, natural language understanding, face recognition processing, cart management, and order processing. The third tier is the data tier which includes the Firebase Real-time Database, file system storage for face images, session storage, and product inventory management.

Core technologies used in the voice assistant system include: Frontend technologies HTML5, CSS, JavaScript, Bootstrap for responsive design, WebRTC for real-time audio and video capture, and the Web Speech API for speech recognition. Backend technologies include the Python Flask framework, Firebase Real-time Database, OpenCV for face detection and processing, DeepFace for face recognition, and pyttsx3 for text-to-speech synthesis. Authentication and security include multi-factor authentication, Session management, Base64 encoding for image storage, and the HTTP protocol for secure communication.

A. Data Collection

The data collection process for implementing the voice assistant includes loading data from datasets like VGG-Face, Facenet, and OpenFace for performing face recognition, and then pre-assigned keywords are used for basic voice assistant operations, which include keywords

like 'Products,' 'Order,' 'Stop,' etc. The product name, price, and product information are loaded from the Firebase Real-time Database called Products.

B. Data Preprocessing

The voice-assistant system has a robust data preprocessing pipeline. As the system has to work in crowded and noisy places, data preprocessing is vital for the accuracy of the system. The initial step in the voice assistant operation is capturing a raw image of the user and subjecting it to a quality assessment using OpenCV's face detection cascade classifier. Key preprocessing steps include image quality enhancement by grayscale conversion, contrast normalization, noise reduction, and resolution standardization. This is followed by face detection and alignment via Haar cascade detection, facial landmark alignment, cropping, and geometric normalization. The process of feature extraction is implemented by resizing, pixel normalization, and colour channel standardization. Model-specific preprocessing adapts images for VGG-Face, Facenet, and OpenFace ensuring compatibility. The final decision for face recognition is taken by considering the result from at least two model agreements. pyttsx3 is used for text-to-speech synthesis. WebRTC is used for capturing audio, and video data in real-time, and Web Speech API is used for speech recognition. The speech is converted to text by the pyttsx3 engine, and Fuzzy JavaScript is used to identify commands in the presence of noise and other challenging conditions. Fuzzy JS plays a crucial role in ensuring the reliable operation of the voice assistant by identifying product and keyword matches from user commands.

C. Speech Recognition

Speech recognition is the core of the voice assistant. Speech recognition is implemented by the combined action of WebRTC, Web Speech API, and pyttsx3 engine. WebRTC facilitates the real-time capture of audio and video. Web Speech API facilitates Real-time speech recognition and the pyttsx3 engine helps in speech-to-text conversion. Speech-to-text conversion alone is not sufficient for a fully operational voice assistant; it requires smart filtering of the obtained data. For context-specific applications, we use Fuzzy JS to find the overall match of the speech command with a valid command or a product in the product database. Fuzzy JS tries to find an overall similarity between the spoken command and the products in the database. Each product is assigned a score out of Hundred, and the highest-scoring product is selected for the operation.

Figure 1 : Voice Assistant Workflow

The user command is divided into two-part. Quantity part which will be a numerical value and the next will be a product name that will be validated against the database. Both commands are validated after the Fuzzy JS filtration and scoring. If either part is not recognized by the engine, the user will be prompted through proper exception handling methods. If the user specifies a valid product and quantity, it will be added to the cart database table. If the user proceeds with the payment, the order will be moved to

IV.EVALUATION

The first step in implementing the voice assistant is registering the user's face. The user's face is registered by linking it to their account. The stored image is later used for face verification during logins.

After successful face recognition, the user is provided with an OTP. The OTP serves as a second level of security, making the system more secure. Once authentication is complete, speech recognition is initiated. WebRTC captures the user's commands. The Web Speech API processes speech recognition, and pytsx3 converts the speech to text. The text is then filtered using Fuzzy.js. Valid commands add products and orders to the cart, while other visual operations are executed accordingly.

Figure 2: Voice Assistant Performance Evaluation Report

The figure above shows a detailed evaluation report for speech recognition functionality. It depicts various performance metrics like Accuracy, Average Response Time, Response Time Standard Deviation, Success Rate, and Error Rate. This evaluation clearly shows that the system performs well under different conditions.

V.RESULT

The result obtained by executing the voice assistant showed high accuracy and short response time. It showed a response time of 0.00 seconds, which proves that the system is triggering the response at a very high speed. Its effective filtration and recognition capabilities resulted in an accuracy of 80.00%. The system has a success rate of 80.00% and an error rate of 20.00%.

TABLE I. CLASSIFICATION REPORT

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
cart	1.00	1.00	1.00	2
exit	1.00	1.00	1.00	2
inventory	1.00	0.50	0.67	2
order	1.00	1.00	1.00	2
show products	1.00	0.50	1.00	2
unknown	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
accuracy			0.80	10
macro avg	0.83	0.67	0.72	10
weighted avg	1.00	0.80	0.87	10

The table shown above represents the classification report obtained for the voice assistant. From this, the system's performance can also be considered excellent.

Figure 3: Voice Assistant Command Recognition Confusion Matrix

The figure shown above displays the confusion matrix constructed for voice assistant system.

Figure 4: Screenshot Of Implementation

CONCLUSION

In conclusion the speech recognition system developed performs well with better speech filtration and short response time. the performance evaluation matrices show that the system has low latency in response time and can provide an accuracy of 80.00%. This implies that the system succeeded in accomplishing the desired tasks with a low error rate of around 20.00%. Therefore, the adopted

technology has high efficiency and the scope for future modifications and extensions is significant. It will enhance the overall application performance and provide a better user experience.

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